

STATE AND LAW

IMPLICATION OF STRATEGIES TO PREVENT AN ATTACK ON POLICE ON AND OFF DUTY IN THE FREE STATE SAPS FROM 2018 TO 2021

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Abstract

The convenient non-probability sampling was used to select the sample from a targeted population of forty (40) police officials at the Free State SAPS. The focus was on the experiences, feelings and perception of police constables, sergeants, warrant officers, captains, and colonels at the Free State SAPS. The qualitative approach was used by the researcher to understand, explore or to describe people's behaviour, themes in behaviour, attitude or trends and relations between people's actions. Regardless of the quality service that police officials provide to the public, there is a fear of police killings while they are on or off duty by criminals. Therefore, there has been serious need for a qualitative research study to be conducted to address the ineffectiveness of the current mechanisms in preventing the factors which influence police killings. The use of force by the police is not permitted as outlined in section 49(2) of the national Constitution and the Criminal Procedure Act No. 51 of 1977 of the Republic of South Africa as it leads to police brutality and is frequently life-threatening, since breathing for the victims is obstructed with and during the use of force.

Keywords: Police, Strategies, Prevention, Attack, Free State, South African Police Service, Job Satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

South Africa (SA) experiences high rates of crime and violence (Bailey & Peterson 2022:5). The increased crime rate in South Africa is a fact and a major issue. In SA, the nature of crime is complicated (Chamlin 2019:359). Section 205 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (Act No 108 of 1996) gives the South African Police Service (SAPS) the mandate to protect (Statistics South Africa (Stats SA) 2016:104), fight, and investigate crime; to maintain public order, protect the inhabitants of the Republic and their properties; and to maintain and apply the rules (Civilian Secretariat for Police 2015:39). Over the last two decades, a new model of policing has emerged, emphasising community partnerships as an effective means of combating crime and criminality in SA (Burchell & Milton 2017:69). The government's focus on community policing is reflected in the National Development Plan 2030, which emphasises that community safety must be built through integration and community engagement (Brink 2017:69). The White Paper on Safety and Security underlined that making the society safer is both the state's and residents' common responsibility (Bailey & Peterson 2022:8). Regardless of the quality service that police officials provide to the public, there is a fear of police killings while they are on or off duty by criminals (Civilian Secretariat for Police 2015:47).

Attacks on police officials and killings are defined as a struggle that begins when the victims forcibly assert ownership of a right and concludes with the ultimate rejection of that right (Chamlin 2019:355). As

a result, police are more accountable, and they question the established order of police-suspect relations. Since this is an unlawful act against human beings, the researcher believes that police killings can be classified as a contact crime (Brink 2017:78). Police officers are increasingly becoming victims of crime, and police killings in South Africa have increased since democracy (Bailey & Peterson 2022:12). Police killing is a contact crime, and it is linked to violent crime, hence reducing violence in South Africa will reduce police killings (Stats SA 2016:109).

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Since police killings are an unlawful act that ends the life of a human being, it is considered a contact crime (Chamlin 2019:360). Even after the country's democratic transition, it is evident that the police have become targets of the worst criminality and that police killings are on the rise in South Africa (Bailey & Peterson 2022:18). According to the Deadly Force Executive Summary (2015:26), the rising statistics of police killings have created fear amongst police officers in such a way that they have developed a fear for their life and to perform their duties effectively.

Background to the problem

Before the introduction of the democratic government, police during the apartheid era were called the police force (Chamlin 2019:359). The police force was militant and was full of torture (Brink 2017:69). The police were not friendly towards members of the public and there was no interaction between the police and the members of the public. After the adoption of the new democracy, South African police became the

South African Police Service (SAPS) (Stats SA 2016:48). Community involvement was illustrated in combating crime as police were working together with members of the public (Smit, Minnaar & Schnetler 2014:36). Due to frustrations from poverty, high unemployment rate and poor service delivery, South Africa experienced violent protests and the police were attacked in the protests (Civilian Secretariat for Police 2015:56). Gang-related violence, cash-in-transit, armed robberies, drug and alcohol abuse are factors that influence the members of the community to attack and kill the police (Snyman 2018:87).

Problem statement

It appears that the South African Police Service is not implementing sufficient strategies to prevent attacks on the police (Chamlin 2019:359).

Sub-problems

- Current mechanisms to prevent the factors influencing police killings are ineffective (Snyman 2018:87);
- Police officials are not adhering to safety regulations.
- Members of the public disrespect members of the police.
- There is no progress with engaging the community on police services; and
- There is poor quality of the service provided by police officials due to fear (Stats SA 2016:109).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What is the required procedure for police officers at the crime scene?
- What are the applicable mechanisms for evaluating and monitoring the factors influencing police killings?
- What are the applicable procedures and policies governing police officials?
- What are the factors influencing violence?
- How does police killings affect service delivery?

RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim

- To explore the implications of the strategies to prevent attacks on police in Free State SAPS between 2018 and 2021.

Research Objectives

- To explore the factors influencing police killings in Free State SAPS.
- To monitor and evaluate the implementation of measures to prevent attacks on the police.
- To examine the required police behaviour at the crime scene.
- To describe and identify the applicable mechanisms for evaluating and monitoring the factors influencing police killings.
- To identify and understand the procedures and policies governing police officials.
- To investigate the factors influencing violence.

METHODOLOGY

A research approach is a strategy and technique that includes all elements of research beginning with the general assumptions to the specific data collection, analysis and interpretation procedures (Bachman & Schutt 2017:113). As a result, the research approach is

determined by the nature of the study problem (Welman, *et al* 2015:41). In order to address the research problem, there are three types of approaches, namely, qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approach (Bless & Hignson-Smith 2015:98). For data analysis, there is the deductive and inductive approaches. The qualitative research approach focuses on the use of words, opinions, thoughts, feelings, and behaviours (Struwig & Stead 2011:36). It aims to understand and describe human behaviour rather than explaining and predicting (De Vos *et al.* 2011:65 & Babbie and Mouton 2001:53). The researcher adopted the qualitative research approach as they intended to acquire in-depth details regarding the killing of the police officers in SA, with a special focus on the Free State police officers. In contrast to the quantitative approach, the qualitative approach is less costly and is less complicated during data analysis (Welman, *et al* 2015:56). The participants comprised a small complement compared to quantitative research; hence less time was spent on the collection and analysis of data.

The quantitative approach puts focus on numbers and numerous amounts of participants, and a lot of time is required for data collection and analysis (Bachman & Schutt 2017:114). The qualitative approach was appropriate because the researcher sought to understand, explore or to describe people's behaviour, theme in behaviour, attitude or trends and the relations between people's actions (Cilliers, Davis & Bezuidenhout 2014:14). This approach is characterised by but is not limited to the following:

- People understand through their own frame of reference.
- Own beliefs, predisposition and perceptions are set aside; and
- All people, settings and subjects are worthy of study (Southern Business School 2021:25).

Research paradigm

A research paradigm is the philosophical foundation for a research study (Welman, Kruger & Mitchell 2015:41). On the other hand, Bryman (2021:630) describes a research paradigm as a cluster of beliefs which guide the researcher on what to study, how research should be done and how the results should be interpreted (Cilliers, Davis & Marie 2014:19). It provides a framework of beliefs and interpretations upon which the research's theories and methods are based (Bachman & Schutt 2017:114). Ontology, epistemology, and research methodology make up a research paradigm (Bless & Hignson-Smith 2015:114). Ontology is a paradigm applicable to the qualitative research approach. The paradigm puts emphasis on the philosophy of existence and the assumptions and beliefs that we hold about the nature of being and existence (Bryman 2018:87). Ontology also assists in studying human behaviour. In this study, the researcher explored the causes of and reasons for the killing of police officers as well as the strategies for mitigating police killings. This study was, therefore, exploratory research. Exploratory research is the study of unknown areas. The researchers sought to obtain insights, identify the key concepts, and confirm the assumptions

regarding the attacks and killing of the police (Burns & Grove 2015:231). Burns and Grove (2015:197) further state that exploratory research can also be used to familiarise with unknown situations, conditions, policies, and behaviours. The researchers, therefore, became aware of the new concepts regarding the attacks on the police after conducting this research.

Target group/population

Prior to conducting a research study, the target population must be identified and agreed upon (Bryman 2018:87). The complete collection of units for which survey data will be utilised to form the conclusions is the target population. Based on this, the target population identifies the units which the research findings are intended to be generalised upon (Bachman & Schutt 2017:75). In this study, the targeted population was forty (40) police officials comprising constables, sergeants, warrant officers, captains, and colonels from the Free State SAPS.

Sample frame

A sampling frame is a set or other tool used by researchers to specify their target population (Welman, *et al* 2015:74). A sampling frame is a list of objects from which a researcher might choose the representatives of the target population. Constables, sergeants, warrant officers, captains and colonels were the sampling frame for this study.

Sampling technique

The convenient non-probability sampling was used to select the sample from the targeted population comprising forty (40) police officials at the Free State SAPS (Welman, *et al* 2015:68). The convenient sampling focuses on participants that are readily available and are willing to be included in the study (Bachman & Schutt 2017:42). Convenient sampling is important as the researcher is saved the time to look for participants for the study (Bryman 2018:87).

Sample size

A sample size, according to Maree (2017:110), is a selected number of participants who represent the entire targeted population. In this study, the selected sample size comprised a of four (4) constables, two (2)

sergeants, two (2) warrant officers, two (2) captains and two (2) colonels. A sample complement of 12 police officials was selected to participate in the study (Welman, *et al* 2015:45). Maree (2017:114) states that there is no required quantity expected for participants in a qualitative research study.

DATA COLLECTION

Data collection is the systematic process of gathering and measuring information on the variables in a study to answer the research questions, test the hypotheses, and evaluate the results (Bryman 2018:113). Qualitative research uses several data collection approaches, including observations, textual or visual analysis from books or movies, and interviews (individual or group) (Welman *et al* 2015:48). However, interviews and focus groups are the most utilised methodologies, especially in social research (Bachman & Schutt 2017:114). Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 12 participants since the researcher sought to gain a deep understanding of the beliefs and perceptions on the causes of attacks on the police. Interviews are an important source of information because they give the researcher the opportunity to understand and interpret the participants' answers to specific questions (Du Plooy-Cilliers, *et al* 2014:188).

The same applies to a focus group (Bryman 2018:136). A focus group is a data gathering strategy in which the researcher interacts with a group of six to twelve people. The researcher conducted interviews with the police officials on different dates at their respective workplaces. Each interview was five to 10 minutes long.

Data analysis

According to Burns and Grove (2015:143), data analysis in qualitative research is the process of bringing all the collected data together, sorting in order, and establishing its meaning. The researcher used the content analysis method to transcribe the recordings from the interviews and present the findings. The interviews were conducted with five (12) SAPS members from one of the Free State police stations.

Themes	factors causing police killings				procedures and pol- icies				Applicable mecha- nisms		factors influenc- ing violence	
	Measures	Crime scene	Dangerous	Ensure safety	Principles	Cases of police killings	Governing laws	Safety	PPE	Shooting	Service delivery	
Res 1	X	X	X	X	x	X	x	X	x	x	x	
Res 2	X	X			x	X	x	X	x			
Res 3		X	x	x		x	x			x	x	
Res 4	X	X	x			x	x	x		x	X	
Res 5	X	x		X	x	X	x		x	x	x	

Figure 1: Summary of themes and subthemes

FINDINGS

i. What are the main factors causing police killings?

- How do you view the importance of taking precautionary measures when attending to incidents?

The responses from Participant 1 and 2 indicated that *“precautionary measures are important in relation to saving the lives of both the citizens and yours,”* whereas Participants 3, 4 and 5 placed emphasis on the fact that situations can become worse and result in more danger. Therefore, their responses indicate that it is very important to be cautious when attending to a scene.

- What kind of crime scenes do you think are the most dangerous?

In support of the other three participants, Participant 1 indicated that *“the most dangerous crime scene is cash in transit robberies; and I think hijackings too.”* However, Participant 2 indicated that *“the most dangerous scene is the one that is in progress.”* The participants indicated that with such a scene, the police do not have full information and do not know how to handle it.

- What times of the day do you regard as dangerous for the police during your working shifts?

All participants indicated that *“the night shift is the most dangerous shift.”* This was explained by Participant 2 that this is *“because dangerous instruments cannot be observed because of the darkness.”*

- What are the disadvantages of not being allowed to shoot someone who attacks you simple because they do not have a gun?

Two of the participants indicated that other than having a gun, perpetrators can still use any other weapon to attack the police officers. Participants 3, 4 and 5 indicated that *“the perpetrator may be stronger than the police officer and may overpower them and end up taking the officer’s gun and kill them.”* It was maintained by Participant 3 who revealed that *“Okay, most criminals attack the police because they know that the Criminal Procedure Act does not protect the police most of the time and that the Act does not necessarily have any loopholes. It has loopholes and it does not protect the police. That is why the criminals know that the police will not attack as they are afraid to act, especially when it comes to shooting.”* Participant 1 stated that *“someone can stab you, and you may lose your life. You can be assaulted and suffer serious injuries.”*

- What do you fear the most on your work?

Participant 2 stated that *“I fear most of the things, but mainly, I fear the commanders because most of the time, they are not going protect you, especially when you get that right. My other fear is the feeling that one day I’m going to get killed or injured during the line of the duty. That is what I fear the most.”* The two participants indicated that being hated by fellow police officers for doing the right thing is what they fear the most. It was indicated by one participant that what they fear the most is having their lives compromised.

ii. What are the required procedures for police officers at the crime scene?

- How are you expected to act when the perpetrator is attacking a police officer without a weapon?

The participants indicated that *“as a as a police officer, I’m supposed to protect every person, whether he is a police officer or not, to prevent the loss of life and injuries, as well as using minimum force.”*

- How do you ensure the safety of your life without injuring the perpetrator?

The participants indicated that *“it is important to call for backup and restrain the perpetrator without having anyone injured or killed.”*

- Which principles do you apply when you are at different crime scenes?

Due to the nature of the scene, the participants indicated that *“it depends on the scene.”* They further indicated that *“it is important to be safe as well as containing the scene.”*

iii. What are the applicable mechanisms for evaluating and monitoring the factors influencing police killings?

- How do they determine cases of police killings at your station?

The participant indicated that police killing is *“anyone who killed in the line of duty.”* They indicated that any police killed while at work is regarded as important and is honoured.

- Who is responsible for minimising the increasing rate of police killings?

In support of Participant 3 who indicated that *“I will say firstly, it is the ME, the police officers, and then it will go to the section commander, and then to the station commander until it reaches the national police Commissioner in ensuring the safety of the employees and the safety of the police officers are all scales.”* Other participants indicated that *“the Minister and his cabinet and every police officer who is on duty is responsible for ensuring that their lives are safe to avoid killings.”*

- Who is the most vulnerable police official?

It was indicated by four of the participants *“that female police officers are the ones who are mostly vulnerable.”* However, Participant 3 indicated that every police officer who does not take his or her work serious is vulnerable.

iv. What are the applicable procedures and policies governing police officials?

- Do you have any legal document that governs your actions as a police official?

The participants have indicated that the policies and procedures governing them are *“the Constitution, National Instruction, Criminal Procedure Act, Police Act and also the National Instructions governing us as police officers.”*

- How does your laws protect you when you are attacked by criminals?

The participants indicated that it *“seems like the law is more on the side of the perpetrators than that of the police officers.”* They indicate that the perpetrators have more rights than them.

- How do you feel about the laws governing police officers?

Participants 2, 4 and 5 indicated that “*police officers are mostly governed by the law than criminals.*” They indicated that “*criminals get less sentences whereas officers get more.*”

v. What are the factors influencing violence?

- How do you feel when attending cases of violence?

The participants indicated that they “*get more scared due to the fact that shooting could be required where they can be shot at or get arrested for shooting the perpetrator who could be attacking.*”

Who is allowed to attend the cases of violence within the communities?

Participants 1 and 5 indicated that “*it depends on the nature of the violence as we have different units.*” They further indicated that it is “*the public violence public order police.*”

- How do you ensure your safety during violence?

The participants indicated that “*it is important to put on safety equipment such as shields and bullet proofs.*”

vi. How does police killings affect service delivery?

- What happens at work when one of your officials is killed and cannot come to work during his or her shift?

The participants have indicated that, “*that is the most difficult moment as it affects service delivery and the morale of the officers. It makes them feel unsafe.*”

- Who is affected mostly during service delivery when one of the police officers is killed?

It was indicated that “*both the members of the public and the officers who are supposed to work on the shift are mostly affected.*”

- To what extent does the killing of the police officers affect service delivery at your station?

Three of the participants indicated that “*other members resign, which thus puts more pressure on service delivery. Some of the members are in fear of attending to the complaints by the community.*”

DISCUSSION

The South African Police Service (SAPS) provides a diverse range of services which can be outsourced to various levels of the government (Tshilongamulenzhe 2012:32). Any policing service established by a country has its own set of rules and regulations (Chamlin 2019:359). For countries all around the world, deciding whether to use a single or multiple policing system is a critical policy decision (Van Der Berg & Van Broekhuizen 2012:53). The provisions of the 1996 Constitution and the 1995 South Africa Police Act 68 made it possible to form a national police force for the Republic of South Africa (Snyman 2018:88). The national police agency must be established to work at the national, provincial, and municipal levels of the government, according to Section 206 of the 1996 Constitution (Spector 2017:105).

According to the Constitution, the political responsibility of a member of the cabinet who must be accountable for policing and must define a national policing strategy after conferring with province

governments and taking into account policing needs and priorities should be established (Spector 2017:94). These basic tasks are completely related to the NDP and the SAPS Code of Conduct, ensuring that all persons are kept secure (Tshilongamulenzhe 2012:31). As maintained by Participant 2 who indicated that the legal documents that govern their actions as police officials are “*the Criminal Procedural Act, Police Acts and standing orders.*” This is in relation to the statement rendered by Participant 1 regarding the issue of police officials who attend the cases of violence, stating that “*I think it's every police officer. For example, for public order violence, it's public. Other police and the people are fighting against each other. I can say it's the police at the station level, like the CSC members for the highest robberies. I think it should be a tactical response team.*”

Factors causing police killings.

Apart from the deaths resulting directly from police shootings, police shootings can degrade trust in the government, with most of the major urban riots in the United States (Chamlin 2019:359) over the past century being sparked by grievances over high profile police's use-of-force incidents, causing further damage, injury, and deaths (Van Der Berg & Van Broekhuizen 2012:53). Studies have shown that the police were ill-disciplined and behaving in an inappropriate way which involved unnecessary shootings (SAPS 2016:15). Participant 3 maintained that “*the police officials who are found killed in the line of duty are those who do not take their work and lives seriously.*” The scientific gold standard would be to randomly assign rookies and more experienced police officers to different high-risk areas and compare their discharge rates (South Africa 1997:28). Such randomness is promising good results that they will be effective (Snyman 2018:87). It might also eliminate one of the main reasons of some shootings, with officers being forced into circumstances where they have no choice but to shoot (Tshilongamulenzhe 2012:33).

Job satisfaction

The police' fear of being shot and killed during their work showed dissatisfaction in their job in a study by Spector (2017:105). Job satisfaction is thus more appropriate because it is the result of human values and a variety of institutional circumstances (Spector 2017:98). Employee happiness is broad in the sense that it can emanate from a variety of sources other than the job itself (SAPS 2016:24).

Violence

South African policing encounters numerous difficulties and dilemmas (Snyman 2018:87). The current high incidences of violent crime, public distrust of the police, and political intervention bring challenges to policing and the professional service delivery (SAPS 2016:33). South Africa is currently dealing with an inflow of police brutality cases (Civilian Secretariat for Police 2015:37). Annually, over 5 500 police criminal offenses are reported (Chamlin 2019:359). According to the Annual Report Statistics of the Independent Police Investigative Directorate (IPID), more than 3

500 incidences of torture and assault (police brutality) were reported (Burchell & Milton 2017:68).

This amounts to more than 60 percent of reported occurrences of police brutality (torture and assault), with a four-year average of 65 percent (Spector 2017:94). This suggests that South Africa is still struggling to police democratically after 24 years of democracy (South Africa 1996:28). With such a high number of recorded incidences of police aggression, one would expect a high conviction rate, especially since the IPID oversees the police and ensures that they are held accountable for their actions (Smithson & Stokoe 2015:148).

Laws and policies

Section 205 of the Constitution and the South African Police Service Act of 1995 gives the SAPS its powers and functions (Chamlin 2019:356). This law governs the police service's primary functions, which include preventing, investigating, and combating crime; maintaining public order (Smit, *et al* 2014:36); protecting and securing South Africans and their property; and upholding and enforcing the law (Stats SA 2016:74). The SAPS should be able to change to effect, forecast and activate forces instead of just reacting to them (Bailey & Peterson 2022:22). Such a method is offered through the process of strategic management. It stands for a rational, methodical, and impartial approach to choosing the future course of the SAPS (Brink 2017:69). Lacking a strategy, means that there is no tested course of action for achieving the organisation's desired results in a changing environment without negatively impacting the police officers (Civilian Secretariat for Police 2015:44).

Police strategies

The process by which an organisation uses certain policies, processes, and resources to accomplish its primary goals is known as its strategy (Chamlin 2019:362). Managers frequently allude to a "strategy" as their comprehensive long-term plan for engaging in the competitive environment to accomplish the organisation's goals (Brink 2017:67). It is sometimes referred to as the "game plan" of the organisation (Burchell & Milton 2017:68). A clearly defined strategy offers a framework for achieving a successful goal. Similarly, it offers a framework for managerial choices without going into detail about all potential future resource allocations, including money, people, and material (Bailey & Peterson 2022:23). Daily, a wide range of decisions need to be made by the SAPS management. While several of these choices are tactical responses to everyday problems, others can have a much more profound impact on the organisation's vitality or direction (Civilian Secretariat for Police 2015:39). These are "strategic" decisions since they determine the course of action. The Medium-Term Strategic Framework (MTSF) of 2019-2024 which outlines the strategic goal for the 6th administration of the government, served as the guide for the creation of the Strategic Plan for SAPS for 2020-2025 (Bailey & Peterson 2022:18).

Service delivery

The SAPS is entrusted with maintaining public order, preventing, combatting, and investigating

crimes, protecting, and securing the residents of the Republic and their property, and upholding and enforcing the law (Brink 2017:69). The Service Delivery Improvement Programme (SDIP) of the SAPS aims to enhance community service delivery. The programme aims to instill an atmosphere of participative management and improved community engagement while giving police station commanders helpful resources to enhance service delivery and law enforcement. Other common metrics for measuring police services include the number of arrests and fines handed out (Civilian Secretariat for Police 2015:39). Since detaining criminals and upholding the law by issuing penalties for violations is considered as one of the key objectives of police work, the number of arrests and fines given out by the police is a measure of performance like crime rates (Chamlin 2019:359).

LIMITATIONS

In this study, data was collected through semi-structured interviews only that were conducted in Free State. The collection was limited to five police officials who were on duty as there was no adequate time to engage more participants. The data collected was based on the events which occurred between 2018 and 2021 in the Free State. Some of sampled participants did not want to participate in the study as some of the stations were very busy.

CONCLUSION

Police violence has grown established in policing tactics in the workplace around the world, and South Africa is no different (SAPS 2016:15). Suspects and witnesses are subjected to extreme brutality and cruelty (Tshilongamulenzhe 2012:32), including being suffocated, having a plastic bag placed over their heads to restrict their breathing, and having a tube down their neck or being strangled (Spector 2017:89). This shows that the use of force is permitted by the Constitution in section 49(2) and the Criminal Procedure Act No. 51 of 1977 which leads to police brutality and is frequently life-threatening, as breathing is obstructed and occurs over time (Burchell & Milton 2017:69). This causes hatred to some members of the public and they develop anger towards the police. These members retaliate by killing the police. The SAPS should be able to change to effect, forecast and activate forces instead of just reacting to them. Such a method is offered through the process of strategic management. It stands for a rational, methodical, and impartial approach to choosing the future course of the SAPS. Lacking a strategy means that there is no tested course of action for achieving the organisation's desired results in a changing environment without negatively impacting the police officers. There is a need to review the policies and laws governing police officials when attending to crime scenes. This is since their safety is mostly compromised, and this causes them the fear to do their work without being killed or prosecuted for doing their work. Various cases are causing members of SAPS to experience a great deal of anxiety and concern, which made them feel vulnerable and helpless, owing to insufficient control. According to the study, this is a result of numerous police officers quitting their jobs.

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